

Fatal Head Injuries in Road Traffic Accidents: Autopsy study in Patan hospital.

Srijana Kunwar, Samjhana Ghimire

Department of Forensic Medicine, Patan Academy of Health Sciences

Devendra Palikhe

Department of Forensic Medicine, Pokhara Manupal Teaching hospital

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15769484>

Article Received 19-07-2021 / Article Accepted 23-08-2021 / Article Published 31-08-2021

ABSTRACT:

This study was conducted at Department of Forensic Medicine, Patan hospital among total 150 autopsy cases of head injuries in road traffic accident (RTA) victims over a period of three years (14th April 2018 to 13th April 2021 A.D). The objective of this study was to observe incidences and the patterns of head injury among the RTA victims. Out of 150 cases, 115 were male comprising 76.7% and 35 were female comprising 23.3%. The maximum incidence of RTA was observed among age group of 20-30 years (30%) and the time of incident where most accidents occurred was between 12:00 PM to 04:00 PM (27.30%). Pedestrians were the most vulnerable road occupants (30%), followed by motorcycle rider (26.7%). Out of total 150 cases of head injuries, skull fractures were found in 93 (62 %) cases. The most common bone involved was the temporal bone 40 (43.01 %), followed by frontal 22 (23.65%). Intracranial hemorrhage was seen in 66.66% of total cases. Most common type of intracranial hemorrhage was Subdural hemorrhage (SDH) in 54%, followed by Subarachnoid hemorrhage (SAH) in 31% cases. Fatalities due to head trauma in RTA can be reduced if there is an early detection of injuries and timely intervention.

Key words: Road traffic accident, head injury, autopsy.

INTRODUCTION:

Road traffic accidents today have become an emerging, yet neglected global epidemic. Globally, it is the eighth leading cause of death and is expected to rise to the top five by 2030^{1, 2}. In developing countries, rapidly increasing

motorization is overtaking the relative development of transportation of infrastructure. This fact is the primary reason for the increasing number and rates of injuries following motor vehicle incidents in developing countries^{3, 4}. Nepal adopts a zero-tolerance policy against the use of alcohol while

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How to Cite

Srijana Kunwar, Devendra Palikhe and Samjhana Ghimire. (2021). Fatal Head Injuries in Road Traffic Accidents: Autopsy study in Patan hospital. *International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research*, 2(04), 21-26. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15769484>

driving, which has lowered the incidence of accidents due to driving under consumption of alcohol. While high increment in number of vehicles and bad conditions of road has led to increased accidents⁵.

The statistical data of Kathmandu valley provided by traffic police of Nepal, showed that the total accidents in Kathmandu for the year 17th July 2018-15th July 2020 were 18,571, among which 407 were fatal⁶. Now, world is facing pandemic due to Novel Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) for which social distancing as well as lockdowns are implemented to prevent and control the spread of infection. Even during such restrictions of vehicular movements in Nepal (24 March to 14 June 2020), there were 1,801 incidents of road crashes recorded by the traffic police in 82 days of lockdown from all seven provinces, which included 2,602 vehicles (96% motorized) with 256 deaths and 1,824 injuries (among which 32% were severely injured)⁷. The present study, therefore was conducted to evaluate the pattern of head injury to emphasize on early detection and focus on the rapid treatment of such victims which can decline the rate of incidence of unnatural deaths on roads by vehicles.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

All the deaths due to head injuries in road traffic accidents brought for autopsy in Patan hospital, during the period 2018-2021 (3 Years) were retrospectively studied and analyzed. Further evaluation was based upon the police inquest report and medical records of the deceased victims who got treatments as well.

RESULT:

Out of 218 medico-legal autopsy cases of road traffic accident, 150 (68.8%) had sustained fatal head injuries. Male accounted for 155(76.7%) and 35 were female (23.3%) with proportion of 3:1 (Figure-I). The most common age group was 20-30 years, constituting 30 % of total cases, followed by 30- 40 years, constituting 16% and 10-20 years age, comprising 14.7% (Figure-II). The peak timing of

deaths due to head injuries in fatal road traffic accidents commonly occurred during the period of 12:00 - 16:00 hours followed by 20:00 to 24:00 hours (Figure-III). It is observed that the highest number of road traffic deaths due to head injuries occurred amongst the pedestrians (30%), followed by motorcycle riders (26.6%) and the least is bicycle riders (Figure-IV). In this study, victims who were able to reach the hospital for treatment were 77 (51.30%), followed by spot deaths at the incident site 42 victims (28%) and 31 victims (20.7%) died on to the way to the hospital.

Figure-I: Showing sex distribution of cases of fatal road traffic accidents with head injuries (2018-2021).

Figure-II: Age distribution of fatal road traffic accident victims with head injuries (2018-2021).

Figure-III: Distribution of victims according to time of road traffic accidents (2018-2021).

Figure-IV: Showing distribution of types of victims

Out of total 150 cases of head injuries, skull fractures were found in 93 (62 %) cases. The most common bone involved was the temporal bone 40 (43.01 %), followed by frontal 22 (23.65%) [Table-I]. The total numbers of cases of intracranial injuries were 100, in which subdural hemorrhage was the commonest comprising 54% followed by subarachnoid hemorrhage in 31% of the cases [Table-II].

Skull fracture	No. of cases	Percentage%
Total no. of cases	93	62
Temporal bone	40	43.01
Frontal bone	22	23.65

Parietal bone	8	8.60
Occipital bone	5	5.37
Base of skull	18	19.35

Table-I: Incidence of skull fractures in head injuries due to fatal road traffic accidents.

Intracranial injury	No. of cases	Percentage%
Total no. of cases	100	66.66
Subdural haemorrhage	54	54
Subarachnoid haemorrhage	31	31
Extradural haemorrhage	0	0
Brain contusions	15	15

Table-II: Incidence of intracranial injuries observed during autopsies of fatal RTA.

In present study, the relation between skull fracture and intracranial injury was statistically insignificant, implying that intracranial injury is independent to fracture of skull (Pearson Chi square value (X^2) = .617 and P = .432). However, the odds risk ratio being 1.620 indicates that in skull fracture there is 1.620 times higher chances of having intracranial injuries. During autopsies, epidural hemorrhage was not observed in any of the cases but when medical reports of deceased were analyzed, total 5 cases had epidural hemorrhages which were medically intervened.

DISCUSSION:

Present study included total 150 cases (68.80%) of fatal head injuries due to RTA out of total 218 cases autopsied for fatal road traffic accidents

during three years (2018 to 2021). During first lockdown in Nepal (24 March to 14 June 2020), despite of restrictions in movements of vehicles except in emergencies situation, total 12 cases of RTA were brought for autopsy in our Patan hospital, two of them had sustained head injuries.

In this study, the predominance of occurrence of road traffic accidents among male and female, most vulnerable age group, time of occurrence of accidents are analyzed and compared with other studies along with most common pattern of head injuries. Most commonly affected victims whether pedestrian or occupants of vehicles were also analyzed. Total 77% cases were male victims and 23 % were female with proportion of 3.29:1 were observed. Greater incidences of RTA in males are also seen in other studies similar to ours^{8, 9}. The higher proportion of male over the female could be due to the fact that males are commonly exposed to the streets and they are the major bread owners of the house, who has to be outside his house most of the time. The most vulnerable group affected were 20-30 years of age (45 victims), followed by 30-40 years of age (24 victims) in this study, which is similar to the studies analyzed in India and Nepal where affected victims fall in 20-40 years of age group⁸⁻¹².

A high death rate in this age group is not only devastating to the family involved but is also affecting the economic and cultural growth of a nation. The present study also showed that the highest numbers of victims were pedestrians (30%) which are consistent with the results of researches performed in Nepal, India and Fiji^{8,9,11,13,14,15}. This might be because pedestrians and the vehicles need to share the same lane on most of the roadways. There is lack of zebra crossings, overhead bridge, pavements and traffic lights. Even in their presence, the pedestrians are reluctant to use them.

In a study by Dr Dhaval J. Patel and Gopinath Agnihotram¹⁶, it was found that most of the accidents occurred in the hours 12:01 PM - 06:00

PM in 43.80 % of the cases. Amit D. Modi et al¹⁷, also observed maximum occurrence of road traffic accident between 12:00 PM to 6.00 PM (34.10%). These findings are similar to the maximum incidence that occurred in present study which was between 12:00 PM to 4:00 PM time period (27.30%).

On viewing the bones involved in the skull fracture (62%), temporal bone was most prone to fracture comprising 43.01 % of the cases followed by frontal bone comprising 23.65 %. The study done by Petre Liviu Munteanu et al¹⁸, at the Buzau found that craniocerebral fractures were found in 52% cases of fatal road traffic accident victims. Dr Sunil Kumar Soni et al¹⁰ at Indore found that most common site of fracture was present in frontal bone in 23%, followed by temporal bone in 16.5%. The thinnest area in the outer skull is the temporal bone (4 mm), followed by frontal bone (6 mm), therefore these bones may have been the most common site for fractures.

Sreekanth S. Nair and Nikhil Lakshmanan¹⁹ found in their study that the most common type of intracranial hemorrhage as sub-arachnoid hemorrhage in 84.9%, followed by subdural hemorrhage in 74.5% and intraventricular hemorrhage in 17.92% cases. The least common type of hemorrhage was extradural hemorrhage in 16.98%. Ahmad M et al¹³ found that the most common hemorrhage as SDH in 43%, followed by SAH in 36%. In present study, the most common type of intracranial injury is SDH (54%), followed by SAH (31%). During autopsy cases of extradural haemorrhage (EDH) were not observed but in medical reports of the victims who were taken to hospital had EDH which was surgically intervened. Therefore, to decrease the death due to head injuries, early detection and immediate intervention for better outcome should be implemented with standard protocols in management of such cases.

CONCLUSION:

A multifaceted approach is required for the most effective and long lasting changes to prevent fatalities in road traffic accidents. The focus should be on issue like establishment of provincial safety committees, motorcycle helmet campaigns, traffic injury prevention and education at the school and community levels and establishment of trauma centers. Road should be properly planned and maintained, with the widening of narrower section of the roads.

Building flyovers or underpass at required sites and four lanes of highways. Drivers should be provided with education that pedestrians should be given the highest priority while crossing zebra crossings. And pedestrians should be educated that zebra crossing should always be used while crossing roads. If no pavements or separate lanes are available, pedestrians should be educated to walk by the side of the road facing the oncoming vehicles. This will enable the pedestrians and the drivers to face the oncoming vehicles. This will enable the pedestrians and the drivers to take prompt action in case of possible collision.

Speed is a critical risk factor for road traffic injuries which was specially analyzed during lockdowns where roads were empty and vehicles were at their maximum speed leading to fatal accidents. Enforcement of speed limit is essential to make them truly effective. Advanced trauma centers with well-equipped infrastructure and support by a team of surgeons, especially neurosurgeons and vascular surgeons at major government hospitals are the cornerstones for the effective management of road traffic accident cases.

REFERENCES:

1. Murray CJL, Vos T, Lozano R, et al. (1990-2010). Disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) for 291 diseases and injuries in 21 regions, : a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. *Lancet* 2012;380:2197–223.doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(12)61689-4
2. Ameratunga S, Hajar M, Norton R. Road-traffic injuries: confronting disparities to address a global-health problem. *Lancet* 2006;367:1533–40. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(06)68654-6
3. Krug E. ed. (1999). Injury: a leading cause of the global burden of disease. Geneva : WHO. http://www.who.int/violence_injury_prevention/index.html
4. Jacobs G., Aaron-Thomas A.&Astrop A. (2000). Estimating global road fatalities. London: Transport Research Laboratory. (TRL Report 445)
- 5.<https://doi.org/numbehttps://nepalpolice.gov.np/images/statistic/webpage/index.html>
- 6.<https://traffic.nepalpolice.gov.np/index.php/news/traffic-activities/425-annually-accidental-descriptions>
7. Sedain B, Pant PR: Road Traffic Injuries in Nepal during COVID-19 Lockdown_ Media reporting and Police record (24 March to 14 June, 2020).csv. figshare. Dataset. 2020. <http://www.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.12958373.v3>
8. Sonawane S. Jambure M. Pattern of head injuries in road traffic accidents-An autopsy study. *International Journal of Current Research*. 2015; 7(12):23733-23737
9. Kalougivaki J.J.V.P., Goundar R.P.S. Retrospective autopsy based study of fatal road traffic accidents in Fiji. *Journal of Forensic Research*. 2014;5(6):1-6
10. Soni S.K. et al. Pattern and Distribution of Head Injuries in fatal road traffic accidents in indore region of central India. *Scholar Journal of Applied Medical Sciences*. 2016; 4(5D):1711-1716
11. Jha S. et al. The pattern of fatal head injury in a teaching hospital in eastern Nepal.*Journal of*

Clinical and Diagnostic Research. 2011;5(3):592-596

12. Kumar A. et al. Fatal road traffic accidents and their relationship with head injuries: An epidemiological survey of five years. Indian Journal of Neurotrauma. 2008; 5(2): 63-67

13. Ahmad M. et al. Postmortem study of head injury in fatal road traffic accident. Journal of Armed Forces Medical College, Bangladesh. 2009; 5(2):24-28

14. Patil S.B. et al. Pattern of head injuries in Road traffic accidents. BioMedResearch. 2014; 1(1):1-5

15. Kual A. et al. Fatal road traffic accidents, study of distribution, nature and type of injury. Journal of Indian Academy of Forensic Medicine. 2005;27(2):71-76

16. Patel D.J., Agnihotram G. Study of road traffic accidental deaths (RTA) in and around Bastar region of Chhattisgarh. Journal of Indian Academy of Forensic Medicine. 32(2):110-112...(15 B)

17. Modi A.D. et al. Demographic profile of head injury cases in Bhavanagar region, Gujarat. International Journal of Research Medicine. 2014;3(3):154-157

18. Munteanu P.L. et al. Pattern of head injuries in lethal road traffic accidents in Buzau country. Roman Journal of legal Medicine. 2014; 22:9-12

19. Nair S.S., Lakshmanan N. Pattern and distribution of head injuries in victim of fatal road accidents-an autopsy based study. Indian Journal of Forensic and Community Medicine. 2017; 4(1):41-45

DECLARATION: I declare that this article has not been published elsewhere.

Conflicts of Interest: Nil
